

POSTBUCKLING FAILURE ANALYSIS OF CARBON/EPOXY COMPRESSION PANEL

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SUMMARY: A finite element methodology that was developed at the Cooperative Research Centre for Aerospace Structures in Australia is applied in the present work for the failure analysis of a postbuckled composite stringer/skin compression panel. Stress analyses are carried out with a global-2D/local-3D finite element model utilising both linear and nonlinear material formulations. Failure analyses on the basis of several phenomenological failure theories lead to failure loads, locations and modes that compare very favourably with results from an experimental test program carried out earlier. Based on the computational results, recommendations for a design improvement of the critical panel region are made. They are consistent with previous empirically derived design changes. The current work suggests that failure initiation in postbuckled composite stringer/skin panels can be effectively modelled with the developed finite element methodology.

NOMENCLATURE

Superscripts, Subscripts and Operators

0	Global coordinate system
e	Effective
$_{x,y,z}$	Cartesian coordinates
$_{1,2,3}$	Ply coordinates
$\bar{\square}$	Vector or Matrix
$\dot{\square}$	Time derivative

Vectors, Matrices and Tensors

ε_{ij}	Strain tensor
$\dot{\varepsilon}_e^I$	Effective inelastic strain rate vector
$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij}^I$	Inelastic strain rate tensor
\underline{R}^{**}	Rotation matrix
$\underline{\Omega}_{ij}$	Back stress tensor
S_{ij}	Deviatoric stress tensor
$\sigma_{ij}, \sigma_{ij}^*$	Applied stress tensors

Scalar Values

E, G	Young's modulus and shear modulus
f	Failure index
ε, γ	Direct and indirect strain
K_2, Z	Overstress and drag stress
M, P	Moment and force
N	Shape function or force flow
ν	Poisson's ratio
σ, τ	Direct and indirect stress
x, y, z	Cartesian coordinates
ξ, η, ζ	Intrinsic coordinates
u, v, w	Translational degrees of freedom
$\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$	Rotational degrees of freedom
b, h, l, t, w	Geometric dimensions
A, B, C, P	Node numbers
$A, D_0, n, f_1, f_2, m, Z_0, Z_1, \Omega_s, C_{ij}$	Material parameters
$X_T, X_C, Y_T, Y_C, Z_T, Z_C, S, R, T$	Material allowables

INTRODUCTION

Computational methodologies based on 2D-plate finite element theory were developed in order to support the postbuckling design certification of composite stringer/ skin panels. However, at critical stringer/skin interfaces the accuracy of 2D-plate models is doubtful. Here a structural discretisation based on plate-type elements represents a severe simplification of the real (physical) situation. To overcome the limitations of standard 2D-plate models special purpose 2D and Quasi3D models were developed. These models are computationally more efficient but involve a significant amount of engineering approximation(s) which complicates the interpretation of results. Global-2D/local-3D analysis procedures were suggested as a feasible alternative. Using these procedures the global domain of a structure is modelled with 2D-plate finite elements and a critical local domain is modelled with 3D-solid finite elements.

A postbuckling failure analysis methodology for composite stringer/skin panels based on a global-2D/local-3D approach was developed at the Cooperative Research Centre for Aerospace Structures (CRC-AS) in Australia [1-3]. The methodology was applied in the work that is presented here (in short: the current work) for the failure analysis of a stringer/skin box beam compression panel. The panel investigated failed in experiments through delamination at the stiffener run-outs. Previous finite element simulations [4] concentrated on the analysis of panel deformation and surface strain distribution. The current work aimed to analyse failure load, failure location and failure mode.

TEST SPECIMEN

The composite panel under investigation was fabricated from unidirectional carbon/epoxy CIBA GEIGY/FIB-REDUX 914-TS-5-34 tape that contained T300 high tensile TORAYACA carbon fibres. The panel consisted of a quasi-isotropic skin and blade-type stiffeners that were equally spaced across the working section. A total of five panels were manually layed up and cured in an autoclave using hard tools. The overall panel was made larger than the actual working section to allow panel attachment to a box beam test fixture. The stiffener ends were trimmed back to avoid interference with the test rig. A description of the panel geometry is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Test panel geometry

Skin regions between the stiffeners were made from eight plies and the stiffeners were made from sixteen plies of unidirectional tape. A symmetric stiffener lay-up was employed. This resulted in a skin lay-up that alternated between being symmetric in some skin bays and unsymmetric in other skin bays, Figure 2 refers. The top three skin plies wrapped from the skin on to the stiffener in order to make the stiffener form a more integral part of the skin.

Figure 2 Schematic of ply stacking sequence

APPARATUS AND TEST

Five stringer/skin panels were structurally tested utilising a four point box beam test rig. The test rig consisted of a three bay aluminium box beam, a supporting steel frame and two 20,000 lb load jacks operated in load control. The jack loads induced a constant bending moment into the middle bay where the test panel was located, Figure 3 refers. The test panel was loaded by a distributed force, N , that acted in the plane of the box beam covers.

The middle bay of the box beam contained a detachable skin which allowed for different test panels to be mounted via a mechanical fastening system.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

A global 2D-plate finite element model of the compression panel, previously developed in [4], formed the basis for the current investigation. The loading and support conditions for the physically existing panel were translated into the finite element boundary conditions presented in Figure 4.

Figure 3 Box beam test rig

Figure 4 Global 2D finite element model

A local 3D-solid finite element model was developed for the current investigation that represented a critical panel region at the central stiffener run-out, Figure 5 refers. Individual plies were therein modelled with separate layers of hexagonal solid elements. Pentagonal solid elements were employed when necessary in order to generate an overall rectangular solid mesh.

Figure 5 Local 3D finite element model

Each solid element on it's own represented a discrete amount of composite material with constant fibre orientation.

The global 2D model and the local 3D model were connected with the coupling technique presented in [1]. The fundamental equations for the coupling technique were originally developed for the general interface node arrangement shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6 General interface node arrangement

Plate nodes (A),(B) and (C) are situated on the edge of a plate element that is adjacent to a solid element region. Point (i) is situated on the intersection between the line that connects (A) and (C) and the line through solid element node (P) that is orthonormal to line (A)-(C). The displacements of point (i) can be related to the displacements of nodes (A),(B) and (C) by employing the following plate shape functions given by Schaeffer [5]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_A &= -0.25(1 + \xi_i \xi_A)(1 + \eta_i \eta_A)(1 - \xi_i \xi_A - \eta_i \eta_A) \\
 N_B &= +0.50(1 + \xi_i \xi_B)(1 - \eta_i^2) \\
 N_C &= -0.25(1 + \xi_i \xi_C)(1 + \eta_i \eta_C)(1 - \xi_i \xi_C - \eta_i \eta_C)
 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The relation between nodal point displacements at plate nodes (A),(B),(C) and displacements at point (i) is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_i &= N_A \cdot u_A + N_B \cdot u_B + N_C \cdot u_C \\
 v_i &= N_A \cdot v_A + N_B \cdot v_B + N_C \cdot v_C \\
 w_i &= N_A \cdot w_A + N_B \cdot w_B + N_C \cdot w_C \\
 \varphi_{xi} &= N_A \cdot \varphi_{xA} + N_B \cdot \varphi_{xB} + N_C \cdot \varphi_{xC} \\
 \varphi_{yi} &= N_A \cdot \varphi_{yA} + N_B \cdot \varphi_{yB} + N_C \cdot \varphi_{yC}
 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The kinematic relation between solid node (P) and point (i) can be defined by applying the assumptions of Kirchhoff [6] plate theory. The displacements of node (P) are herewith expressed in terms of the displacements and rotations of point (i), viz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_P &= u_i + h \cdot \varphi_{yi} \\
 v_P &= v_i - h \cdot \varphi_{xi} \\
 w_P &= w_i
 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Substitution of Eqs. (2) into Eqs. (3) relates degrees of freedom on solid element node (P) with degrees of freedom on plate element nodes (A), (B) and (C), viz:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{Bmatrix} u_P \\ v_P \\ w_P \end{Bmatrix} &= N_A \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_A \\ v_A \\ w_A \end{Bmatrix} + N_B \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_B \\ v_B \\ w_B \end{Bmatrix} + N_C \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_C \\ v_C \\ w_C \end{Bmatrix} \\
 &+ N_A \cdot h \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varphi_{yA} \\ -\varphi_{xA} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + N_B \cdot h \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varphi_{yB} \\ -\varphi_{xB} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} + N_C \cdot h \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varphi_{yC} \\ -\varphi_{xC} \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Thus far the equation development was carried out with reference to a plate element coordinate system. The previous equations can not be used in a general context where element coordinate systems and global coordinate system often not coincide. To eliminate this restriction Eq. (4) was formulated in global coordinates by employing the rotation matrix \underline{R}^{**} :

$$\begin{aligned}
 \begin{Bmatrix} u_P^0 \\ v_P^0 \\ w_P^0 \end{Bmatrix} &= N_A \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_A^0 \\ v_A^0 \\ w_A^0 \end{Bmatrix} + N_B \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_B^0 \\ v_B^0 \\ w_B^0 \end{Bmatrix} + N_C \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} u_C^0 \\ v_C^0 \\ w_C^0 \end{Bmatrix} \\
 &+ N_A \cdot h \cdot \underline{R}^{**} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varphi_{xA}^0 \\ \varphi_{yA}^0 \\ \varphi_{zA}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + N_B \cdot h \cdot \underline{R}^{**} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varphi_{xB}^0 \\ \varphi_{yB}^0 \\ \varphi_{zB}^0 \end{Bmatrix} + N_C \cdot h \cdot \underline{R}^{**} \cdot \begin{Bmatrix} \varphi_{xC}^0 \\ \varphi_{yC}^0 \\ \varphi_{zC}^0 \end{Bmatrix}
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The previous mathematical approach formed the basis for a generic coupling program which can be used as a pre-processor for a variety of finite element codes, viz: MSC/NASTRAN [7], ABAQUS [8], etc. The coupling program reads a basic data input file and automatically identifies solid element nodes that are situated within a plate/solid interface control volume. The program generates, based on the physical location of plate nodes (A), (B) and (C), the appropriate multi-point-constraint (MPC) statements for solid element nodes that are found within the control volume. The multi point constraint statements are automatically added, in the required format, to the basic data input file of the employed finite element program. This modified data file can then be processed in a normal fashion without solver modifications being required.

Employing this program the global-2D and local-3D models of the box beam compression panel were connected. The coupling program required eight-noded plate-bending elements in order to work. They were simulated by substituting three triangular elements for each four-noded element found at the plate-solid interface, Figure 7 refers.

Figure 7 Interface nodes on stiffener and skin

MATERIAL MODEL

Aircraft structures that are made from fibre reinforced composite materials are generally designed such that the fibres carry the bulk of the applied load. The associated in-plane material behaviour is termed fibre-dominated. In a classical composite design a strain limit of around 0.4 % is applied to prevent breakage of the brittle fibres. Within this strain limit the material behaves essentially linear-elastically and the material behaviour can be mathematically expressed with nine elastic constants, Table 1 refers.

Table 1 Material constants for T300/914C [9]

E_{11}	E_{22}	E_{33}
131.90 GPa	9.51 GPa	9.43 GPa
G_{12}	G_{13}	G_{23}
5.27 GPa	7.03 GPa	3.39 GPa
ν_{12}	ν_{13}	ν_{23}
0.326	0.341	0.485

Composite fibres carry far less load in situations where a force flow exists through the thickness of the material, i.e. at free edges, lap-joints or at skin-stiffener interfaces. The associated interlaminar material behaviour is termed matrix-dominated and requires a nonlinear material description for representing the viscoplastic material behaviour of polymeric matrix material, see Mills [10].

A theory by Ramaswamy & Stouffer [11] was employed in the current work to model matrix behaviour. The theory consists of three equations. The first equation represents the constitutive relation between the inelastic strain rate $\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^I$, the Deviatoric stress S_{ij} , the ‘back stress’ Ω_{ij} , the ‘drag stress’ Z and the effective value of the ‘overstress’ K_2 :

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^I = D_0 \cdot \exp \left[-\frac{A}{2} \cdot \left(\frac{Z^2}{3 \cdot K_2} \right)^n \right] \cdot \frac{(S_{ij} - \Omega_{ij})}{\sqrt{K_2}} \quad (6)$$

The second equation models the development of the ‘back stress’ - the ‘back stress’ being the level to which an applied stress relaxes during a prolonged strain hold.

$$\dot{\Omega}_{ij} = \frac{2}{3} \cdot f_1 \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^I - f_1 \cdot \frac{\Omega_{ij}}{\Omega_s} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_e^I + f_2 \cdot \dot{S}_{ij} \quad (7)$$

The third equation models work hardening. This is done by introducing a ‘drag stress’ that depends on the amount of accumulated inelastic work, viz:

$$\dot{Z} = m \cdot (Z_1 - Z) \cdot S_{ij} \cdot \dot{\epsilon}_{ij}^I \quad , \quad Z_{(0)} = Z_0 \quad (8)$$

An additional equation was added by the authors to account for materials with non-zero post yield slope, viz:

$$\sigma_{ij}^* = \sigma_{ij} + C_{ij} \cdot \left(\varepsilon_{ij} - \frac{\sigma_{ij}}{G_{ij}} \right) \quad (9)$$

In this equation, C_{ij} represents the post-yield slope parameters and G_{ij} represents the elastic shear moduli of the material.

The material model is adapted to individual materials by specification of material model parameters: $A, D_0, n, f_1, f_2, m, Z_0, Z_1, \Omega_s$ and C_{ij} . The material model parameters for T300/ 914C were identified with an optimisation procedure [12] that gradually reduced the error between the simulated material response and the experimentally measured material behaviour. The recovered material model parameters are presented in Table 2.

Table 2 Material parameters for T300/914C

A	D_0	n	f_1	f_2
1	5e9 1/s	0.237	2.4e4 MPa	0
m	Z_0	Z_1	Ω_s	C_4
0	2.9e5 MPa	2.9e5 MPa	65 MPa	310 MPa

The previous mathematical description formed the basis for a material user routine for the program ABAQUS that is called during element stiffness updates.

The following assumptions were made to simplify the FEM implementation of the material model:

1. Only the matrix dominated stress terms $\sigma_{22}, \sigma_{33}, \tau_{12}, \tau_{13}$ and τ_{23} contribute to viscoplastic material behaviour;
2. In a first order approximation the direct stresses σ_{22} and σ_{33} are assumed to be linear functions of the direct strains ε_{22} and ε_{33} , (see Jones [13]);
3. The nonlinear shear behaviour is similar in the three material planes, (see Alesi et al [12] and Nguyen [14]).

The previous assumptions lead to a constitutive model that contains a linear-elastic/orthotropic representation for the direct stress components and a nonlinear-inelastic/iso-tropic representation for the indirect stress components. The composite material model was implemented by adding the current material model to an existing ABAQUS user subroutine developed by Trippit et al [15].

Several material simulations were carried out in order to validate the material model for strain rates that cover five orders of magnitude - ranging from quasistatic loading to shock-type loading. The finite element results for a single solid element model are compared in Figure 8 with the experimental stress-strain curves.

Figure 8 Material shear response

STRESS ANALYSIS

Geometric nonlinear finite element analyses were carried out in the current work with both linear and nonlinear material models. Initial imperfections consistent with the first buckling mode were generated by small lateral forces in order to bias the nonlinear solution to follow the experimentally observed load path.

In the linear material analysis with NASTRAN an exponential increase of stress for at least four stress components was observable in the vicinity of the stiffener tip. This pointed towards a stress singularity. This interpretation was verified by carrying out numerical convergence tests with different stiffener tip mesh sizes. Here it was found that some tip stress components increased dramatically when reducing mesh size. The problem was overcome in a material nonlinear analysis with ABAQUS. In this simulation the material plastified and load was shed to less stressed areas. Employing a nonlinear material model resulted in an overall less ‘spiky’ stress distribution and a converged stress solution. Figures 9-11 contain interlaminar stress results for one of the 90-degree skin/stiffener plies at the stiffener run-out.

Figure 9 Interlaminar peel stress σ_{33}

Figure 10 Interlaminar shear stress τ_2

Figure 11 Interlaminar shear stress τ_{31}

FAILURE ANALYSIS

Several more commonly used three-dimensional composite failure theories [16-21] were employed for a prediction of stiffener run-out failure. The associated material strength allowables for T300/914C are presented in Table 3.

The stress results from a geometric and material nonlinear finite element analysis of the global-2D/local-3D model were employed for calculating failure indices for individual solid elements. The failure indices were then used to determine the actual failure load. For a comparison between the computational and experimental failure loads refer to Table 4.

Table 3 Material allowables for T300/914C [9] [MPa]

Material allowable	Symbol	Value
Tensile strength in fibre direction	X_T	1328.0
Compression strength in fibre direction	X_C	1064.0
In-plane transverse tensile strength	Y_T	70.9
In-plane transverse compression strength	Y_C	221.0
Interlaminar peel strength	Z_T	97.6
Interlaminar compression strength	Z_C	242.0
In-plane shear strength	S_{12}	71.2
Interlaminar 1-3 shear strength	R_{13}	94.5
Interlaminar 2-3 shear strength	T_{23}	52.9

Table 4 Comparison of failure loads [N/mm]

Failure Theory	* P_{limit}	** P_{limit}	*** P_{limit} (Test Panel)
1. Max. Stress	106.85	153.74	204.00 (BP01)
2. Hill	75.16	127.94	184.00 (BP03)
3. Hoffman	91.22	178.49	211.00 (BP06)
4. Tsai-Wu	84.26	150.79	187.00 (BP06B)
5. Hashin	75.84	157.98	158.00 (BP10)
6. Quad. Stress	101.49	158.08	
Average values	89.13	154.50	188.80

*FEM Linear Material, **FEM Nonlinear Material, ***Experiment

Four segments of solid elements within the stiffener tip region are displayed in Figure 12. The dark areas represent finite elements with a failure index of greater than one.

From the previous graph it can be seen that at design load, $N=200$ N/mm, critical stress levels occurred only within a very small structural domain in the vicinity of the stiffener run-out tip. Critical stress levels were found in solid elements within the stiffener and the skin in 0-degree plies and also in some solid elements within the 90-degree stiffener plies. This result is consistent with a c-scan image that was taken after the panels had failed experimentally, Figure 13 refers. Here it can be seen that delamination mainly occurred around the stiffener run-outs. The delaminations in the most left skin bay were formed during final panel collapse.

Figure 12 Computational failure locations

Figure 13 C-scan of stiffener run-out area

Table 5 Critical element stresses [MPa]

Elem.	σ_{11}	σ_{22}	σ_{33}	σ_{12}	σ_{13}	σ_{23}	f*
3030	-1376	-15	-74	55	9	-2	1.8
3252	-1384	-40	-86	44	33	13	1.7
6582	-1375	-15	-74	56	-8	2	1.8
6804	-1382	-40	-85	45	-33	-13	1.7
3031	-891	-15	-62	66	10	-4	1.2
6583	-891	-15	-62	66	-9	4	1.2
1515	-313	-12	-37	81	9	-10	1.2
2130	-313	-12	-37	81	-9	10	1.2
12310	-817	-31	-60	82	32	-6	1.6
12311	-709	-18	-58	90	6	-7	1.7
12312	-709	-18	-58	90	-5	7	1.7
12313	-818	-32	-60	82	-32	6	1.6
2747	57	-26	-13	-15	-25	-65	1.3
2752	54	-26	-13	-15	25	65	1.3
12309	84	-82	-76	-42	-26	-62	1.2
12314	84	-82	-76	-42	26	62	1.2

*f=Failure Index

Inspection of the stress components shows that three different failure mechanisms were active at the stiffener run-out, viz: Zero-degree plies under the stiffener, i.e. element 3030-6804, failed in a pure in-plane compression mode and combined compression and shear mode (elements 3031 & 6583). Zero-degree plies within the stiffener, i.e. element 1515-12313, failed due to in-plane (the term ‘interlaminar’ is equally valid at this model location) shear failure. Ninety-degree plies within the stiffener, i.e. element 2747-12314, failed due to interlaminar shear failure.

The information contained in Table 5 allowed the following failure interpretation: The loading mechanism and overall panel response in combination with a relatively small skin bending stiffness resulted in strong skin bending deformations at the stiffener run-out. This resulted in high compression stress being induced in the upper zero-degree plies at the stringer/skin transition. Loading through the skin essentially generated a lap joint problem at the stiffener run-out where compressive skin load had to be transferred via shear into the zero-degree stringer plies. One part of this load was transferred through in-plane shear within the zero-degree skin/stringer transition plies another part via interlaminar shear within the 90-degree stiffener plies into the assembly of zero-degree stringer plies.

Figure 14 contains a photo of the three inner blade stiffeners. Post-failure inspection of the area showed that the stiffener run-out separated from the skin. The stiffener run-out also split at the interface between the ‘block’ of zero-degree stringer plies and the top three stringer/skin cover plies. Both of these experimentally observed failure mechanisms are consistent with the computationally predicted failure modes.

Figure 14 Delamination at stiffener run-outs

CONCLUSIONS

A global-2D/local-3D finite element methodology previously developed at the CRC-AS was employed in the current work for failure analysis of a postbuckled composite stringer/ skin panel. An existing global 2D-plate finite element model of the complete panel was employed in combination with a local 3D-solid finite element model of a critical stiffener region. The global and the local model were kinematically coupled to form a combined global-2D/local-3D finite element model of the panel. Herewith geometric and material nonlinear finite element analyses were carried out. Critical stresses were computed for a region at the tip of the stiffener run-out. The stress state in individual plies was of complex three-dimensional nature. This justified the modelling detail employed in the development of the local 3D model. It is believed that with a plate-type finite element discretisation of the stiffener run-out it would not have been possible to capture the local structural response at the run-out tip.

The three-dimensional stress-strain response of the composite material that was used for the manufacture of the investigated panels was determined in an experimental test program. The material showed strong viscoplastic shear behaviour including nonlinear stress-strain curves and other phenomena such as rate sensitivity, stress relaxation and creep. A viscoplastic material theory was employed for the mathematical representation of this material behaviour.

A linear material analysis of the box beam compression panel produced stress results that were singular at the critical panel region. A material nonlinear analysis based on the developed viscoplastic material model produced physically meaningful stress values that could be employed for a quantitative prediction of failure initiation.

The predicted failure loads for the investigated load case were very close to the ones observed in the experiments, Figure 15 refers. In fact both the computational results for buckling load and failure initiation represent conservative estimates of the experimentally observed values. These findings suggest that failure initiation in postbuckled composite structures can be effectively modelled with the developed global-2D/local-3D finite element methodology.

Stress components and failure indices for solid elements that were identified as being critical are presented in Table 5.

Figure 15 Summary of results

The failure analyses further pinpointed at which plies and through which failure mechanism failure occurred. The computational results for failure location and failure mode compared thereby qualitatively very favourably with the experiments. Previous empirical design improvements of the investigated panels were based on a close inspection of experimental results. Premature failure of the stiffener run-out was there overcome by reinforcement of the panel skin and by subdivision of the zero degree stringer sublaminates. The first measure reduced local skin curvature. The second measure increased the effective shear area, resulting in a more effective load transfer between skin and stringer. The computational results from the present work support both of these changes.

The positive findings from the current work indicate that the developed nonlinear global-2D/local-3D finite element procedure can be employed as part of a general postbuckling composite design methodology.

REFERENCES

1. Alesi, H., Jones, R., Mileskin, N., A technique for coupling plate and solid elements, Proc. Comp. Mech. 95, Vol. 1, Eds. S. N. Atluri, G. Yagawa, T. A. Cruise, Springer Verlag, ISBN 3-540-59114-1, pp 702-707, 1995.
2. JONES, R., ALESI, H., CHIU, W. K., GALEA, S., A preliminary study into the matrix dominated non-linear behaviour of graphite/epoxy laminates, Composite Structures Vol. 30, pp 193-199, 1995.
3. Alesi, H., Thomson R. S., Diegelmann, G., Jones, R., Experimental and computational skin/stiffener analysis of a postbuckled graphite/epoxy shear panel, Proc. First Australasian Congress on Applied Mechanics, The Institution of Engineers Australia Preprints of Papers, pp 273-278, Melbourne, 1996.
4. Trentin, C., Scott, M. L., Alesi, H., Postbuckling behaviour of blade-stiffened fibre composite panels, Proceedings 9th International Conference on Composite Materials, pp. 511-518, Madrid, 1993.
5. Schaeffer, H. G., MSC/NASTRAN Primer Static and Normal Modes Analysis, Wallace Press, pp 143-145, Milford New Hampshire, 1988.
6. Kirchhoff, G. R., Ueber das Gleichgewicht und die Bewegung einer elastischen Scheibe, Journal fuer reine angewandte Mathematik, Vol. 40, pp 51-88, 1850.

7. MSC/NASTRAN Version 66A User Manual Vol. I & II, Editor M. A. Reymond, The MacNeal-Schwendler Corporation, Los Angeles, 1989.
8. ABAQUS Version 5.3 User Manual, Vol. I & II, Hibbitt, Karlsson & Sorensen Inc., Pawtucket, 1993.
9. Benzeggagh, M. L., Khellil, K., Chotard, T., Experimental determination of Tsai failure tensorial terms F_{ij} for unidirectional composite materials, *Composites Science and Technology* 55, Elsevier Science Ltd., pp 145-156, Northern Ireland, 1995.
10. Mills, N. J., *Plastics: Microstructure, Properties and Applications*, Metallurgy and Materials Science Series, Eds. R. W. K. Honeycombe & P. Hancock, Edward Arnold Ltd, pp 153-173, London, 1986.
11. Ramaswamy, V. G., Stouffer, D. C., Laflen, J. H., A constitutive model for the in-elastic multi-axial response of René 80 at 871C and 982C, *Journal of Engineering and Materials Technology*, ASME, 112, pp 281-286, 1990.
12. Alesi, H., Postbuckling analysis of 3D composite structures, Dissertation submitted for examination, Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology, pp 121-153, Melbourne, 1996.
13. Jones, R. M., *Mechanics of composite materials*, McGraw-Hill, pp 339-342, New York, 1975.
14. Nguyen, V. M., Prediction of interlaminar failure in selected Graphite-Epoxy laminates, MEng Thesis, Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology, To be published, 1997.
15. Trippit, B. J., Jones, R., Recent Australian developments in the engineering applications of constitutive modelling, AMD-Vol. 213/MID-Vol.63, *Numerical Implementation and Application of Constitutive Models in the Finite Element Method*, ASME, pp 14-20, New York, 1995.
16. Zocher M. A., Allen D. H., Evaluation of first ply failure in a three dimensional loadspace, *Journal of composite materials*, Vol. 29, No.12, pp 1649-1665, 1995.
17. Hill R., *The mathematical theory of plasticity*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1950.
18. Hoffman O., The brittle strength of orthotropic materials, *Journal of composite materials*, Vol. 1, pp 200-206, 1967.
19. Tsai S., Wu E., A general theory of strength for anisotropic materials, *Journal of composite materials*, Vol. 5, pp 58-78, 1971.
20. Hashin Z., A failure criteria for unidirectional fiber composites, *Journal of applied mechanics*, Vol. 47, pp 329-334, 1980.
21. Brewer J., Lagace P., Quadratic stress criterion for initiation of delamination, *Journal of composite materials*, Vol. 22, pp 114-1153, 1988.